

THE POTENTIAL OF KHIVA IN ZIYARAH TOURISM OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the growing trend of ziyarah tourism in Uzbekistan, focusing on Khiva's potential as a major hub due to its rich Islamic heritage and well-preserved historical sites. By exploring Khiva's unique attractions and historical significance, the study highlights the city's ability to attract pilgrims from around the world, thereby enhancing Uzbekistan's overall tourism industry. This article also discusses how Khiva can promote and contribute to the broader tourism landscape of Uzbekistan.

Introduction

Ziyarah tourism, a type of pilgrimage tourism, is rapidly gaining popularity in Uzbekistan, because of the country's rich Islamic heritage. Among the notable destinations, Khiva stands out with its exceptionally well-preserved historical and religious landmarks. This city holds immense potential to become a central hub for Ziyarah tourism. Ziyarah tourism is a unique form of religious travel in which individuals journey to significant locations such as holy sites, shrines, and the tombs of esteemed figures within the Islamic faith. This practice has deep roots in Islamic tradition. The term "Ziyarah" derives from the Arabic word زيارَة, which means the act of visiting sacred places and revered individuals. [1]

Objectives and methodology

The research will focus on the following objectives:

- Identifying potential Ziyarah tourism destinations in Khiva
- Evaluating the quality of services and amenities from the perspective of Muslim visitors.
- Analyzing the potential economic impact of promoting Ziyarah tourism in Khiva.
- Understanding visitor perceptions and attitudes towards Ziyarah tourism.
- Proposing recommendations for the sustainable development of Ziyarah tourism.

This research adopts a descriptive approach using qualitative methods to achieve its objectives. It involves reviewing information from various relevant sources related to the topic. After gathering this information by observing and reviewing, the analysis is conducted qualitatively, emphasizing explanations and concepts rather than mathematical formulas.

Research findings and discussion

Khiva's establishment and its role in Muslim world

Khiva (Uzbek: Xiva, Хива, خيوه; Persian: خيوه, Xīveh; historically known as Orgunje, Kheeva, Khorasam, Khoesm, Khwarezm, Khwarizm, Khwarazm, Chorezm; Arabic: خوارزم and Persian: خوارزم) is a city in Uzbekistan's Khorazm Region, home to approximately 93,000 people. Archaeological findings indicate that Khiva was established around 2,500 years ago, with its 2,500th anniversary celebrated in 1997. Throughout its history, Khiva has served as the capital of Khwarezmia, the Khanate of Khiva, and the Khorezm People's Soviet Republic. The city's historic district, Itchan Kala, became Uzbekistan's first UNESCO World Heritage Site in 1991. [2]

According to Khudoyberganov (2012), the earliest references to Khiva can also be found in Arab historical and geographical works. Specifically, the 10th-century Arab traveler and scholar Muqaddasi writes: "Khiva is a large city built on the edge of the desert, with a well-maintained Jame Mosque. Kardoronxos and Xazorasp are similar, with wooden gates and surrounded by moats". The fortress of Khiva was built along the Kheyvanik (Kheykanik) canal, which branches off from the Amu Darya River. [3]

The architectural monuments of Khiva are believed to have been constructed over four historical periods. The first period includes the Jome Mosque, a 10th-century monument thought to have been built on the site of the city's fortress walls and a Zoroastrian temple. The second period follows the Mongol invasion by Genghis Khan, featuring 13th-14th century structures like the mausoleums of the three saints and Sayyid Alouddin. The third period of architectural development spans the 16th-18th centuries, during which the country's economic and political activities shifted southward, leading to rapid growth in Khiva. The fourth period of architectural development begins in the last quarter of the 18th century.

Khiva has played a significant role in the Muslim world, both historically and culturally. As a prominent city in the Khorazm Region of Uzbekistan, it has been a center of Islamic learning, trade, and governance. Here are some key aspects of Khiva's role in the Muslim world:

Center of Islamic Learning and Scholarship

Khiva has been a hub for Islamic scholars and learning. It is home to several madrasas (Islamic schools) where students studied various subjects, including theology, jurisprudence, astronomy, and mathematics. Renowned scholars such as Al-Khorezmi, Al-Biruni, a polymath who made significant contributions to science and humanities, were connected to Khiva and its surrounding region.

The construction of madrasahs began to gain popularity starting from the 17th century and reached its peak by the 19th century. The Khorezm madrasahs were 1-2 story buildings with large and beautiful portals, surrounded by cells, and some madrasahs had minarets built next to them. The portals and minarets of the madrasahs were decorated with tiles of various colors, inscribed with verses from the Quran, words honoring the patron, and the date of construction. In the 19th century, there were 120 madrasahs and 63 schools where Quran was taught in the city of Khiva. After the Russian occupation of the Khiva Khanate, their number was halved. At the beginning of the 20th century, their number was 64, and by 1922, it had decreased to 54.

Architectural Heritage

The city is renowned for its well-preserved Islamic architecture. The inner town of Khiva, known as Itchan Kala, is a UNESCO World Heritage Site and features numerous mosques, madrasas, minarets, and mausoleums that reflect the rich Islamic architectural heritage. The Juma Mosque, with its wooden columns, is a notable example of Khivan architecture. Khiva has been a crucial center of Islamic learning, culture, and governance. Its historical significance, architectural heritage, and role in trade and commerce have cemented its place as an important city in the Muslim world.

Minarets as Architectural heritage

The word “minaret” in Arabic means “lighthouse” or “torch”. In Islamic countries, minarets were built next to mosques and madrasahs. Therefore, they are often thought to serve only for calling to prayer. In fact, minarets existed even before Islam and served as “lighthouse” for caravans in the desert along the Great Silk Road. At the beginning of the 20th century, there were 17 minarets in the city of Khiva. [3] Today, 12 of them have been preserved:

1. Juma Mosque Minaret
2. Islam Khoja Minaret
3. Kukhna Muhammad Amin Khan Minaret
4. To'ra Murod To'ra Minaret
5. Sayyid Niyaz Sholikorboy Minaret
6. Polvon Qori Minaret
7. Abdol Bobo Minaret
8. Kabutar Khona Minaret
9. Chilla Avliyo Minaret
10. Muhammad Mahram Minaret
11. Bikajon Bika Minaret
12. To'rt Shohboz Minaret

The minarets that were destroyed between the 1930s and 1950s are as follows:

1. Poyanda Minaret
2. Abdul Karim Aqsakal Minaret
3. Bog'cha, Ibrahim Khoja Minaret
4. Musafir Khona Minaret
5. Muhammad Rahimxon 2 minorasi

Religious Significance

Khiva's mosques and religious institutions have long been important sites for worship and pilgrimage. The city's Jome Mosque and other religious sites have attracted Muslim pilgrims and visitors, adding to its religious significance. Although Khiva has many historical monuments built in Islamic style, here are some religious ones that can be used as pilgrimage tourism destinations:

1. Tohir Eshan Mausoleum
2. Shaykh Muhtar Vali Mosque
3. Sayyid Alouddin Mausoleum
4. Abdulla Mehtar Library

5. Sayyid Ota Mosque
6. Pahlavon Mahmud Mausoleum
7. Mothers' Graves
8. Olvon Poyaki Mausoleum
9. Bobo Horis Mosque
10. Bog'bonli Mosque
11. Jome Mosque
12. Oq Mosque
13. Uch Avliyo Mausoleum
14. Sayyid Niyoz Sholikorboy Mosque
15. Abdol Bobo and Yugurak Bobo Mausoleums
16. Shohimardon Bobo Cemetery
17. Shoqalandar Bobo Complex [3]

Today, Khiva continues to preserve and promote its rich Islamic heritage. Its historic sites and cultural practices remain a testament to the city's enduring role in the Muslim world. Efforts to maintain and restore its architectural and cultural heritage ensure that Khiva's Islamic legacy continues to be celebrated and remembered.

Current Status of Tourism

Since 2017, under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, major reforms have been carried out in the tourism sector in Uzbekistan.

According to the **picture 1** the number of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan was 2.7 million in 2017, 5.2 million in 2022, and 4.3 million in the first nine months of 2023. The average stay of tourists in our country is 4–5 days, which is 1.5 times longer compared to the same period last year.

In addition to direct travel expenses, the average amount spent by each foreign tourist in the country was 197 USD in 2017, which increased to 400 USD in 2023. The volume of tourism exports reached 1.72 billion USD in the first nine months of 2023.[4]

The number of domestic (internal) tourists also grew by 107 percent compared to 2017, reaching 14.9 million.

Picture 1. Number of Foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan

The following countries had the highest number of tourists (**Picture 2**):

- 676 thousand from Russia (1.3 times more compared to the same period in 2022);
- 99 thousand from Turkey (1.4 times more);
- 41 thousand from India (2.9 times more);
- 39 thousand from China (8.5 times more);
- 35 thousand from South Korea (1.9 times more);
- 28 thousand from Germany (1.7 times more);
- 25 thousand from Italy (2.9 times more);
- 22 thousand from the United States (1.8 times more);
- 18 thousand from France (1.7 times more).

Picture 2.

It is emphasized that efforts are being made to increase the number of foreign tourists to 10 million by 2024.

In 2021, within the framework of investment projects in the tourism sector, funds amounting to a total of 11.4 trillion soums were utilized, and 495 projects were implemented. As part of the State Investment Program, in collaboration with local authorities, 62 projects worth a total of 1.2 billion USD were undertaken, with 562.7 million USD in investments utilized and 31 projects launched.

In 2022, a total of 735 projects worth 22.1 trillion soums were launched in the tourism sector, creating nearly 23,000 new jobs in the industry. As a result of the attention given to developing entrepreneurship, attracting investment, and establishing competitive services, leading hotel brands such as Hilton, Marriott, Hyatt, Wyndham, InterContinental Hotels Group, and Accor are entering our tourism market. They are expressing interest not only in the capital city of Tashkent but also in the cities of Bukhara, Samarkand, and Khiva, establishing their operations there. [4]

Challenges and recommendations

Promoting ziyorah tourism in Khiva involves overcoming several challenges. Here are some of the primary obstacles:

1. Lack of Awareness

Many potential tourists, especially from Muslim-majority countries, may not be aware of Khiva's significance as a ziyorah destination.

In order to overcome this barrier, *marketing campaigns* should be launched targeting Muslim-majority countries to highlight Khiva's religious and cultural significance.

In addition to this, *tourism fairs* and *exhibitions* are also should be organized. Participating in international tourism fairs and exhibitions can promote Khiva as a ziyorah tourism destination.

For this reason, in 2022, during the 11th session of the tourism ministers of the member states of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) held in the city of Baku, the ancient city of Khiva, which has a history of over two and a half thousand years, was declared as the “Tourism Capital of the Islamic World” for 2024. [5]

In connection with this event, Khiva quickly attracts the attention of the entire Islamic world. Within the framework of influential events taking place in Uzbekistan, the 12th session of the tourism ministers of the OIC member states was held. During the session, presentations on the tourism potential of the member countries of the OIC were made, the results of implemented projects were analyzed, and future strategies were discussed.

It is necessary to emphasize that granting the status of the tourism capital of the Islamic world to Khiva provides an opportunity to position the city as one of the best tourist centers in the international tourism market. UNESCO experts even compare Khiva with ancient cities such as Athens, Rome, and Cairo. Also Khiva has been awarded the esteemed title of Islamic Heritage Destination of the Year by Crescent Rating in 2023. This significant recognition highlights Khiva’s rich cultural and historical importance, as well as its dedication to preserving its Islamic heritage.

2. *Cultural Sensitivity*

Authorities should ensure that tourism development respects and preserves the local culture and religious practices.

To tackle this challenge, *the authority should consider community involvement*. Because engaging local communities in tourism planning to ensure their needs and cultural practices are respected.

Another way to deal with this is *to educate tourists about local customs and religious practices* in order to foster respect and understanding.

By addressing these challenges with targeted strategies, Khiva can significantly enhance its appeal as a ziyorah tourism destination. Collaborative efforts between the government, private sector, and local communities will be crucial in realizing this potential.

Conclusion

Promoting Ziyorah tourism in Khiva requires a multifaceted approach that combines infrastructure development, strategic marketing, cultural preservation, and community engagement. By implementing these strategies, Khiva can attract more pilgrims and tourists, fostering economic growth and cultural exchange while preserving its rich heritage for future generations. By focusing on these areas, Khiva can attract more pilgrims and tourists, contributing to its economic and cultural development.

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